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2012

NATIONAL EVOLUTIONARY SYNTHESIS CENTER
ANNUAL REPORT

DIRECTOR'S MESSAGE

Yesterday I welcomed a new working group to NESCent, one focusing on the evolution of virulence in human infectious disease using HIV as a case study. For most of the participants, including the three PIs - Viktor Müller of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences, and Josh Herbeck and Geoff Gottlieb of the University of Washington - this was their first time at NESCent. The same was true of a hosted meeting on ciliate biodiversity held at NESCent the previous week, organized by John Clamp of North Carolina Central University. We are always pleased to have new participants here, and indeed, our participant "discovery curve" shows no sign of flattening (Figure 6.4). New participants bring new disciplinary and cultural perspectives to the center, and infuse our research with vitality and freshness. Additionally, with each new participant, NESCent realizes its mission: to connect, share and transform. These are the foundations of our program, whether we are thinking of data, ideas, concepts, whole disciplines, or people.

NESCent has had another good year. In the following pages you will read about our science, informatics and education/outreach activities, but it is important to acknowledge that we had a good year because of the community that supports us, and the people who come through our doors. In the end, NESCent is a partnership between those of us at the center, and the scientists, students, educators and journalists who contribute their time and efforts to delivering the outcomes that make an imprint on the present and future of evolutionary science.

What happens next year? NESCent's core funding from the National Science Foundation comes to an end in December 2014. No one we have spoken to wants to see NESCent close the shutters and turn off the lights. So, in 2013, we will continue to make the case that a synthesis center such as NESCent is precisely the kind of vehicle that has the highest probability of taking a high-risk, high-reward idea and delivering significant and potentially transformative outcomes. If you read the rest of this document, I think you will agree that this is an easy case to make.

Allen Rodrigo :: 26 September 2012

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HUNDREDS OF ARTICLES ON NESCENT SCIENCE HAVE APPEARED IN MAINSTREAM MEDIA OUTLETS INCLUDING SCIENCE MAGAZINE, NPR, SCIENTIFIC AMERICAN, DISCOVERY CHANNEL, WIRED, THE NEW YORK TIMES, AND TIME MAGAZINE

SINCE ITS BEGINNINGS IN 2004, NESCENT HAS HOSTED NEARLY 4,500 VISITORS FROM MORE THAN 50 COUNTRIES

\$22,777,000: ADDITIONAL GRANT SUPPORT OBTAINED BY SCIENTISTS SINCE 2007 AS A DIRECT RESULT OF THEIR INVOLVEMENT WITH NESCENT

MORE THAN 40% OF NESCENT PUBLICATIONS OCCUR IN LEADING JOURNALS FOR EVOLUTIONARY SCIENCE (E.G., NATURE, SCIENCE, TRENDS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION, PROCEEDINGS OF THE ROYAL SOCIETY B, PROCEEDINGS OF THE NATIONAL ACADEMY OF SCIENCES, USA, ECOLOGY LETTERS, EVOLUTION, SYSTEMATIC BIOLOGY, GENETICS, AMERICAN NATURALIST)

PAPERS STEMMING FROM NESCENT-SPONSORED PROJECTS HAVE BEEN CITED MORE THAN 8,000 TIMES SINCE THE CENTER'S BEGINNINGS IN 2004

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

NESCent continues to be a vibrant and productive center, and our science, informatics and education and outreach programs continue to serve the science community, educators and the general public. As we approach our last year of funding from the National Science Foundation in 2014, we and others in the evolutionary science community are keen to identify ways for NESCent to continue to provide the services and resources that foster innovative and potentially transformative research. The fact that our funding is time-limited constrains our plans and the way we operate. Consequently, we have held discussions with our supporting institutions, the scientific community, federal funding agencies and foundations to discuss opportunities for programmatic or center-wide support. We have met with some success, and in 2013, we will have a more concrete idea of what the future holds for NESCent. Regardless of what this future might be, though, we are determined to provide the best opportunities for novel science to flourish until we close our doors.

SINCE 2005, NESCENT HAS HOSTED MORE THAN
200 WORKING GROUP AND CATALYSIS MEETINGS

A close-up photograph of a light-colored snake, possibly a corn snake, showing its head and the intricate pattern of its scales. The snake's eye is visible, and its mouth is slightly open, revealing small teeth. The scales are a warm, golden-brown color with a glossy sheen. A dark purple rectangular box is overlaid on the right side of the image, containing white text.

As we approach our last year of funding from the National Science Foundation in 2014, we and others in the evolutionary science community are keen to identify ways for NESCent to continue to provide the services and resources that foster innovative and potentially transformative research.

NESCent supports research and education across disciplinary, institutional, geographic, and demographic boundaries

SCIENCE & SYNTHESIS

NESCent science includes a broad portfolio of scientific activities spanning a wide range of organisms, habitats, methods, and disciplines. Our program continues to draw support and enthusiasm from the community. In year 8, NESCent's Calls for Proposals attracted 94 proposals for Working Groups, Catalysis Meetings, Sabbaticals, Postdoctoral Fellowships, or Courses; this represents an increase of 21 over 2011. NESCent supported 33 scientific meetings in year 8 (20 Working Group meetings and 7 Catalysis meetings), involving 610 visitors. The center hosted 16 postdoctoral fellows, 5 sabbatical scholars, 1 Triangle research fellow, 15 short-term visitors, 5 graduate students, and several visiting and resident scientists. The collaborative and energetic science supported by NESCent continues to attract attention, as evidenced by NESCent's h-index (a metric reflecting citation frequency; currently at 43). In the past two years we have introduced four targeted initiatives in Evolutionary Medicine, Synthetic Biology, Evolution and the Social Sciences, and K-12 Evolution Education for Underrepresented Minorities. In these categories we have supported catalysis meetings, working groups, sabbatical fellows, and short-term visitors.

In 2013, we will also hold two meetings for which we have received supplemental funding: (1) a meeting for the evolutionary developmental biology community, to review the developments in the field, and to survey possible future directions; and (2) a "Women Evolving Biological Sciences" meeting focusing on career development in the biological sciences.

The end of formal National Science Foundation funding in December 2014 means that we will no longer call for postdoctoral fellowship proposals (our last call was in July 2012) and working group proposals (last call December 2012) in 2013, unless there is an infusion of funds for the center and/or these programs.

INFORMATICS

Informatics staff at NESCent continues to serve the needs of the center's sponsored science, and strengthen cyberinfrastructure capacity for synthetic evolutionary science. In 2012, NESCent supported the digitization of the data from Thomas Park's classic mid-20th century experiments on competition in *Tribolium* beetles, a project proposed by Sabbatical Scholar Michael Wade of Indiana University. We also assisted with the development of a series of teaching modules based on these data, and others from Dryad, to bring data into college and university classrooms. Also, in 2012, the first of three planned hackathons for the Working Group: "HIP: Hackathons, Interoperability, Phylogenies" was held.

NESCent again served as a Google Summer of Code mentoring organization and oversaw eight student projects in the summer. Two additional summer internships were conducted under the auspices of DataONE. NESCent continued to support the iEvoBio Conference, which held its 3rd meeting in July in Ottawa. NESCent was the site of a number of hosted informatics meetings, including two related to the development and use of ontologies for anatomical and phenotypic information, and two board meetings for not-for-profits incubated by the center (i.e., the Phylinformatics Research Foundation and Dryad).

NESCent has received new awards from a variety of agencies (the NSF, NIH, and Sloan Foundation) for projects including the Dryad Digital Repository, the NSF AVAToL-funded Open Tree of Life project, the Generic Model Organism Database community support desk, and impactstory.org.

EDUCATION AND OUTREACH

NESCent's education and outreach activities represent a dynamic blend of established programs and new initiatives/partnerships. Outreach to the education community continued to include established NESCent programs such as the Darwin Day Roadshow, the annual NABT Evolution Symposium, teacher training workshops, Evolution in the News web stories and podcasts, and our popular evolution film festival. NESCent once again held its annual Darwin Day event at the NC Museum of Natural Sciences, and other sponsored talks and events for the public. NESCent also provided support to underrepresented minorities via organized activities at the annual meeting of the Society for Advancement of Chicanos and Native Americans in Science (SACNAS), multiple travel award/scholarship programs, our targeted initiative in K-12 evolution education for underrepresented minorities, and a program called Seeing and Learning Science After-school (SALSA). Internationally, NESCent's Ambassador program has now sent nearly 20 NESCent scientists to eight different countries in developing regions around the world to conduct short courses, workshops and teacher training. The NESCent Academy offered three new courses and one pre-existing course aimed at imparting informatics skills. It also hosted the 2012 GMOD Summer School.

In the coming year, we will continue to maintain our collection of existing activities and education/outreach resources, while simultaneously piloting, developing and exploring new opportunities. For example, we will conduct after-school science activities in Korean, launch the recently-completed Spanish language translations of our *Evolution in the News* stories, and expand the Ambassador program into Brazil (while returning to Belize, Bali, Kenya and Ecuador). We will also aggressively pursue funding opportunities that will enable us to continue our education/outreach programs after 2014.

COMMUNICATIONS

NESCent's communications program continues to provide scientists with opportunities to deliver the results of their research to a broader audience. In the past year NESCent-sponsored science appeared in more than 90 news stories in the mainstream media, including *Science Magazine*, *NPR*, *Scientific American*, *Discovery Channel*, *Wired*, *The New York Times*, and *TIME Magazine* (compare to 65 stories in the 2010-2011 reporting year, and 40 stories in 2009-2010). In 2011-2012 we hosted two journalists-in-residence: Award-winning essayist Ilan Greenberg, who interviewed experts for a series of articles about emerging infectious diseases with animal origins, and freelance journalist Michael Martin, whose reporting on the unusual life and work of evolutionary biologist Margie Profet was covered by the *New York Times* and *Psychology Today*.

ASSESSMENT

NESCent's assessment activities during the previous year combined maturing our assessment portfolio while developing new initiatives to measure our impact on the broader scientific community. One area of strategic focus at NESCent is the extension of our assessment activities to showcase the added value of the synthesis center model to funding agencies and organizations that may not already be aware of NESCent. Together with the National Center for Ecological Analysis and Synthesis (NCEAS), NESCent also supports and participates in a cross-center assessment working group (Advancing Theory and Research on Scientific Synthesis). Our assessment continues to show that NESCent-supported research is having an impact. In Year 8 we have so far produced 115 papers – compared to the 89 papers from last year at this time. In the last year, these papers have garnered an additional 3,509 citations for a cumulative total of 8,220 (an average of 17.53 citations per publication; up from 16.13 citations per publication in 2011). Similarly, our data indicate that of the 554 subdisciplines and 13 disciplines in science (classified according to an analysis of the contents of a wide range of journals), NESCent publications occur in 121 and 12, respectively.

In our Science of Science project, run in collaboration with Dr. Jonathon Cummings, a total of 1242 surveys have been collected from participants at 1st, 2nd, 3rd, and 4th working group meetings. Very preliminary trends point to differences between large and small meetings with, for instance, participants in larger groups having a lower probability of forming collaborations than those in smaller groups.

Administratively, there have been some changes to NESCent's personnel. Amongst these was Phillip Grosshans, our Assistant Director for Administration, who moved to take a permanent position at another center at Duke University. NESCent also lost two members of the informatics staff, Vladimir Gapeyev and Sandra Hall. Also in 2012, Todd Vision, our Associate Director of Informatics, was on sabbatical leave. Joel Kingsolver of UNC-Chapel Hill assumed that role while Todd was away. Brian Wiegmann, our Associate Director for Education and Outreach, began his sabbatical leave in July 2012, and Dr. Jenny Xiang of NCSU, is presently the Acting Associate Director for Education and Outreach. We place on record our thanks to all those who have left NESCent – they have had a significant impact on the work that we do, and we are very grateful for their contributions.

In the coming year, we will work to make sure that our staff is well-trained and competitive. We will also begin planning for Evolution 2014, which NESCent is organizing in collaboration with faculty from the wider academic community in North Carolina.

115 PAPERS HAVE BEEN PUBLISHED BY NESCENT-SPONSORED SCIENTISTS IN THE PAST YEAR

HIGHLIGHTS

As in previous years, there has been no shortage of innovative and exciting work at NESCent. Here are just a few highlights from our Science, Informatics, and Education and Outreach programs:

NOT JUST FOR THE BIRDS: MAN-MADE NOISE HAS RIPPLE EFFECTS ON PLANTS, TOO

A growing body of research shows that birds and other animals change their behavior in response to man-made noise, such as the din of traffic or the hum of machinery. But human clamor doesn't just affect animals. Because many animals also pollinate plants or eat or disperse their seeds, human noise can have ripple effects on plants too, finds a new study. This story was picked up by Scientific American, the Christian Science Monitor, MSNBC, National Public Radio, Audubon Magazine, the Miami Herald, BBC News, Science News, Discovery News, and the New York Times.

MAPPING THE BIRTHPLACE OF THE WORLD'S LARGEST LANGUAGE FAMILY

Using phylogeographic methods for tracking the origin and spread of virus outbreaks, NESCent researchers have mapped the birthplace of the Indo-European language group, a family of hundreds of languages and dialects spoken by nearly three billion native speakers throughout Europe and Asia. The findings, published in the August 24, 2012 issue of Science, suggest that the language family arose 8,000 to 9,500 years ago in present-day Turkey – and help solve a longstanding debate in language evolution.

DEVELOPING SOFTWARE TO ACCESS THE TREE OF LIFE

The Phylotastic project—launched at a NESCent hackathon in June—aims to develop software, standards and strategies to provide computable, convenient, and credible access to the Tree of Life. The Phylotastic hackathon brought together 30 diverse participants from many different institutions, including NESCent, iPlant, BioSync, to help bring to fruition an ecosystem of loosely coupled software components that together can deliver to end-users (e.g. community ecologists, genomicists) subsets of knowledge about the tree of life on demand. A variety of demonstration projects from this event – the first of three planned hackathons – are on display at evoio.org/wiki/Phylotastic. While in the past NESCent has organized hackathons on particular topics at the urging of sponsored scientists, this is the first instance in which the plans for such an event were written directly into the proposal for a sponsored science project.

MEASURING SCHOLARLY IMPACT BEYOND THE LIBRARY AND THE LAB

If you're a scholar, how do you know if the work you do is influential? Researchers, universities and publishers have traditionally measured the impact of scholarly work by counting the number of publications, and how often those publications have been cited. But in a world where research comes in many forms, citations are only part of the story. What traditional impact metrics don't catch are scholarly contributions that don't come in standard journal article form, such as datasets, software and code, all of which influence research and teaching in ways that aren't reflected in the citation record. A new movement called altmetrics – short for alternative metrics – aims to provide a more complete and timelier picture of all the different ways that scholars contribute to their field and the impact and reach of their work. Altmetrics tools such as ImpactStory (impactstory.org/) collect and display a wide range of usage information, including citations, page views, data downloads, blog posts, media coverage, and other indicators that the work is being noticed.

The system aggregates impact data from many sources and displays it in a single report, which is given a permanent URL for dissemination and can be updated any time.

Despite its young origins – the project grew out of a May 2011 Beyond Impact workshop sponsored by the Open Society Foundations, Wellcome Trust and the JISC – ImpactStory received wide recognition through its entry to the 2011 PLOS-Mendeley binary battle, has been reported in media outlets from the Chronicle for Higher Education to the Guardian, and recently was awarded funding from the Sloan Foundation for continued development. NESCent incubated ImpactStory from the start as a way to help assess the center's own broader impacts.

NESCENT HITS THE ROAD FOR DARWIN DAY 2012

As part of NESCent's Darwin Day Roadshow (roadshow.nescent.org), NESCent scientists/educators again visited schools in small communities in Oregon, Washington, Arkansas, Missouri, Louisiana and West Virginia to celebrate Charles Darwin's birthday. The visits focused on research at NESCent and careers in science. This year, the program grew significantly, receiving over 100 applications from 27 states.

ENABLING SCIENTISTS AND EDUCATORS IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES TO MAKE THE MOST OF THEIR DATA

Thanks to a two-year, \$246,515 grant from the National Science Foundation, NESCent is collaborating with local partners in communities worldwide to offer hands-on training in data management, data analysis and other issues through an outreach initiative called the NESCent Ambassador Program (ambassadors.nescent.org). The goal of the program is to enable scientists in developing

countries to use existing informatics tools to make the most of the data they collect. In addition to offering short (one to two-week) courses and workshops, NESCent provides one-on-one and small group consultation to local scientists in the field, classroom, or computer lab, using their actual datasets. This year the program grew and expanded, with several new or continuing international programs that included:

- The Caribbean—Four NESCent scientists/educators and collaborator Elvis Nuñez from the Univ. of Florida visited K-12 and undergraduate institutions in Jamaica, Trinidad, Barbados and Belize to deliver workshops on evolutionary science and evolution education.
- Kenya—NESCent ambassadors conducted a two-week workshop on computational phyloinformatics at the Kenya Medical Research Institute (KEMRI), run by the Wellcome Trust in Kilifi, Kenya.
- Galapagos—NESCent scientists conducted a series of evolution education/outreach workshops for elementary school students and teachers, as well as Galapagos guides.
- Bali—For the second year in a row, NESCent ambassadors conducted a two week workshop on phylogenetic inference for Indonesian scientists and graduate students at the Indonesian Biodiversity Research Center.

As the original grant wraps up, we are exploring ways to sustain and expand the program, which has now matched US-based scientists with scientists and communities in eight countries in the Caribbean, South America, Asia and Africa. To find out more about NESCent workshops offered around the world, and how you can get involved, visit ambassadors.nescent.org/.

A NEW STUDY FINDS THAT MAN-MADE NOISE HAS RIPPLE EFFECTS ON PLANTS SUCH AS PIÑON PINE, WHOSE NATURAL SEED DISPERSERS TEND TO AVOID NOISY AREAS.

HEATHER PIWOWAR, CO-CREATOR OF IMPACTSTORY

NESCENT AMBASSADOR PROGRAM

PRESENT-DAY DISTRIBUTION OF THE INDO-EUROPEAN LANGUAGES

DARWIN DAY

1. CENTER-WIDE INITIATIVES

FOCUS ON THE FUTURE: NESCENT SUSTAINABILITY POST-2014

In 2012, we continued our focus on the future – what happens to NESCent when National Science Foundation funding formally ceases in November 2014? To figure this out, we worked with our collaborating institutions, scientific societies, our colleagues in the scientific community, funding agencies and foundations. In this section, we describe what we have done, what we have achieved, the challenges ahead, and our plans for the next year.

1.1 2012 ACTIVITIES

1.1.1 MEETINGS WITH OUR PARTNER INSTITUTIONS

NESCent's Oversight Committee consists of senior administrators from Duke (Dr. Robert Calderbank, Dean of Natural Sciences, and Jim Siedow, Vice-Provost for Research), UNC-Chapel Hill (Dr. Carol Tresolini, Vice-Provost for Academic Initiatives), and NCSU (Dr. Chris Brown, then Assistant Vice-Chancellor for Research Development), as well as the Chair (Dr. Rick Ree) and Vice-Chair (Dr. Vicki Funk) of NESCent's Advisory Board. All members of the Oversight Committee, except Dr. Vicki Funk (who was on sabbatical leave at the time) met with the Directors at NESCent on 28 – 29 March 2012.

The Oversight Committee is charged with evaluating the performance of the directors, and with providing strategic advice on NESCent's priorities. As expected, this meeting was dominated by a discussion of NESCent's future, and in the Committee's report to the National Science Foundation, they clearly identify three of the challenges we face:

- NESCent's activities are winding down, and the scientific community is taking notice. July 2012 was the last call for proposals for postdoctoral fellowships, and December 2012 will be the last call for working group proposals.
- NESCent will continue to have difficulty retaining critical staff. Staff losses this year include three from the informatics team as well as our Assistant Director for Administration.
- NESCent is further hamstrung in its ability to secure funding because qualified staff at the center are not able to apply for external funding as PIs because of the limited term of their employment.

NESCent also presented members of the Oversight Committee with a draft outline of our projected expenses post-2014 and a bottom-line contribution from the partner institutions that would offset these costs. There was extensive discussion of this document, and the Committee recommended that NESCent convene a meeting of senior leaders from the three institutions, to explain how NESCent adds value to the Triangle and the broader scientific community, and to begin a conversation about NESCent's future.

The Senior Leaders' Meeting was held at NESCent on 22 August 2012. More than 30 representatives from Duke, UNC-CH, and NCSU were present, including provosts, vice-provosts, vice-chancellors, deans, chairs of departments, and directors of other research centers. Amongst the facts and figures that were presented at this meeting, the following stand out as being particularly demonstrative of NESCent's value to the partner institutions:

· FACULTY FROM DUKE, UNC-CH, AND NCSU HAVE ATTENDED BETWEEN 22 – 44% OF NESCENT WORKING GROUPS, AND BETWEEN 29 – 56% OF NESCENT CATALYSIS MEETINGS.

· DUKE, UNC-CH, AND NCSU FACULTY ARE AUTHORS ON 6 – 10% OF NESCENT PUBLICATIONS, IN JOURNALS WITH IMPACT FACTORS RANGING FROM 3.5 – 8.2.

· NESCENT HAS BROUGHT IN MORE THAN \$11M OF EXTERNAL FUNDING TO THE THREE PARTNER INSTITUTIONS.

We have had some informal feedback since the meeting, and the advice is that ongoing institutional support will have to fit with the programmatic and thematic priorities of the partner institutions. We will work with the three institutions to identify what these are and how NESCent can contribute.

1.1.2 MEETINGS WITH THE SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY

On May 24 – 25, 2012, NESCent hosted a “mini-summit meeting” with nine participants from the evolutionary science community, including representatives from the evolution societies, other research centers, and universities. There were two reasons for the meeting:

- a. We wanted to know if there were new and innovative ways of promoting synthetic evolutionary science that we were not already doing; and
- b. We wanted to hear what a cross-section of the evolutionary science community had to say about NESCent and its future.

The feedback we received was valuable. All participants agreed that there was an “unqualified” need to have a synthesis center, and that NESCent has played a significant role in the evolutionary science community. The participants saw NESCent as a place where potentially groundbreaking areas of research came from the community, where researchers could come together to focus on the science and identify commonalities and differences across disciplines, and where strong interactions with informatics staff lead to the downstream benefits of training for postdocs and graduate students. The participants also identified areas that NESCent may want to develop. For instance, can NESCent's resident community of postdoctoral fellows, sabbatical scholars and short-term visitors become more involved in working groups and catalysis meetings? How can we ease the transition of synthesis-centric postdocs back to field or lab biology? Should we expend more energy on meeting facilitation? How can we restructure our education and outreach program to take more advantage of a wider field of NESCent-affiliated scientists? Should NESCent facilitate contact amongst researchers at appropriate conferences? These and other suggestions are currently under consideration.

With respect to NESCent's future, the meeting also generated a wealth of suggestions, from endowed or named postdocs, to the possibility of a subscription model for NESCent. There was also discussion about how corporations and foundations may be encouraged to support synthetic research. Again, these suggestions are just some of the suite of potential opportunities that we are evaluating.

1.1.3 MEETINGS WITH FUNDING AGENCIES

In November 2011, NESCent was invited to make a presentation at the National Science Foundation. On 14 November, we spent the day at the National Science Foundation where we spoke about NESCent science, informatics, education and outreach. The presentation was well received by the attendees, and we were able to expand on the role that NESCent plays in the community.

Dr. Dan Janes, a program officer at the National Institute of General Medical Sciences (NIGMS), one of the National Institutes of Health, was present at the National Science Foundation meeting, and invited us to visit NIGMS to talk about NESCent, its mission and its operations. Program officers at NIGMS were enthusiastic, and we were invited to submit a pre-proposal to develop a Biomedical Technology Resource Center (BTRC) focusing on evolutionary biomedicine. We submitted a pre-proposal for a BTRC that aims to develop community resources in biomedically-relevant evolutionary science, using the synthesis center model as its framework. We are still waiting to hear the outcome of that pre-proposal.

1.1.4 FOUNDATIONS

Over the last year we have worked with the Duke Foundation Relations office to build a strategy for identifying foundations whose goals and mission overlap with NESCent, and actively engaging such foundations. In the past six months, we have had discussions with program officers at several foundations, and we have met with some success. The Sloan Foundation provided funds to NESCent and a DataONE postdoctoral fellow, Heather Piwowar, to develop a web-based resource that provides information on the total impact of researchers' works (see Informatics section). We are also currently working with Sloan on their Indoor Biome initiative. After discussions, we were encouraged to submit a proposal to seek support for a catalysis meeting on the evolution of the indoor biome. The grant proposal has been submitted and is awaiting review.

1.2 2013 PLANS

As we think about NESCent's future, we are also committed to thinking about how we can best serve the evolutionary science community, given the constraints of time, funds and staff. Although we are concerned about sustainability, we want to ensure that we continue to deliver the resources and services that the community has come to expect. Whereas some programs will end unless we can secure future funding, we fully intend to ensure that NESCent continues to remain a vibrant center, where researchers have the opportunity for lively, engaging, and stimulating intellectual discourse.

In 2013, we will continue to work with potential funding agencies, with the partner institutions, with foundations and corporations, and with the broader community to figure out how we can keep our activities going. We are not blind to the possibility that NESCent will not continue much longer after 2014, and we have already worked out contingency transition plans. By the end of 2013, we will be in a much better position to know what NESCent's future holds.

2. SCIENCE AND SYNTHESIS

NESCent's core science programs – postdoctoral fellows, long-term and short-term visiting scholars, and teams of scientists we have supported in Working Groups and Catalysis meetings – enable NESCent-supported scientists to tackle many important evolutionary problems using synthetic methods. Our in-house community is a fertile environment for sustained research and allows diverse scientists to identify common interests and stimulate new collaborations.

2.1 2012 ACTIVITIES

Much of the science done at NESCent has a high impact within the scientific community; NESCent-sponsored science tends to be published in high-impact journals, and NESCent's h-index (a metric reflecting citation frequency) is high, currently at 43 (see “Assessment” section). In addition to

the stories already listed in the Highlights, other successful NESCent science stories of the past year include:

WHY NOT MARRY YOUR COUSIN? MILLIONS DO

The health risks of marrying a cousin have been grossly overstated, says a new book that examines common misconceptions about cousin marriage. A better understanding of the health effects of cousin marriage could mean more appropriate marriage laws and better medical care for cousin couples and their children, says author and NESCent visitor Alan Bittles. Picked up by West Australia Today and The West Australian.

ICE AGE COYOTES WERE SUPERSIZED COMPARED TO COYOTES TODAY

Coyotes today are pint-sized compared to their Ice Age counterparts, finds a new fossil study. Between 11,500 and 10,000 years ago – a mere blink of an eye in geologic terms – coyotes shrunk to their present size. The sudden shrinkage was most likely a response to dwindling food supply and changing interactions with competitors, rather than warming climate, researchers say. Picked up by the Huffington Post, Wired, MSNBC, and Science Magazine.

BIRDS IN UNCERTAIN CLIMATES ARE MORE LIKELY TO STRAY FROM THEIR MATES

Married people may pledge to stay faithful through good times and bad, but birds sing a different tune – when weather is severe or uncertain, a new study finds that birds are more likely to stray from their mates. The results could mean more marital strife for birds coping with climate change, the researchers say. Picked up by Discovery News, Huffington Post, Scientific American, Globe and Mail, and the New York Times.

PREHISTORIC PREDATORS WITH SUPERSIZED TEETH HAD BEEFIER ARM BONES

The toothiest prehistoric predators also had beefier arm bones, finds a new fossil study. Picked up by the History Channel, Discover Magazine, MSNBC, Science Magazine, the MSNBC/Huffington Post, Nature and the UK's Daily Mail.

NESCent has hosted more than 200 working group and catalysis meetings since 2005.

2.1.1 SUPPORTED SCIENCE

In year 8, NESCent's Calls for Proposals attracted 94 proposals for Working Groups, Catalysis Meetings, Sabbaticals, Postdoctoral Fellowships, or Courses; this represents an increase of 21 over 2011. Of these 94 applications, 26 were supported (see Appendices for summary).

We also attracted 26 applications for Short-term Visits and Graduate Fellowships in year 8 (up from 17 in year 7). Of these 26, 20 have been supported. The complete list of NESCent scientific projects funded in year 8 is given in the Appendices.

In the aggregate as of September 15th 2013, NESCent supported 33 scientific meetings in year 8 (20 Working Group meetings and 7 Catalysis meetings), involving more than 600 visitors. In addition we hosted 6 meetings by a variety of groups involved in evolutionary synthesis not supported by NESCent funds. A complete list of meetings at NESCent in year 8 is given in the Appendices.

2.1.2 THE NESCENT IN-HOUSE COMMUNITY AND POSTDOCTORAL DEVELOPMENT

We have maintained a vibrant and collegial community of in-house scientists. During year 8, the center will have hosted 16 postdoctoral fellows, 5 sabbatical scholars, 1 Triangle research fellows, 15 short-term visitors, 5 graduate students, and several visiting and resident scientists. We have also continually worked to improve the mentoring and professional development program for our postdoctoral fellows. Each entering postdoctoral fellow meets with a mentoring committee to discuss the postdoctoral fellow's research plans, NESCent expectations, local and other resources; and the development of a written mentoring plan for each postdoctoral fellow.

In addition, we run an ongoing postdoctoral professional development program that included the following activities this year:

- A three-day NESCent Postdoctoral Retreat. This is the third year we have run this retreat. It included two half-day workshops on effective college teaching, as well as targeted sessions on topics such as the navigating the publishing process, switching research focus/career paths, avoiding scientific jargon, surviving your first year as a faculty member, and maintaining a presence in social media, as well as multiple structured sessions to discuss research.
- A Postdoctoral Professional Development Seminar Series throughout the year, including recent sessions on “Negotiating your first faculty position,” “Scientific publishing from the inside out,” “Responding to critiques of your publications,” “Discussing synthesis in evolution,” “Open access/open data,” and “The job application.”

2.1.3 NEW INITIATIVES IN 2012

In the past two years we have introduced four targeted initiatives to jumpstart new areas of evolutionary synthesis: Evolutionary Medicine, Synthetic Biology, Evolution and the Social Sciences, and K-12 Evolution Education for Underrepresented Minorities. Our K-12 Education initiative is discussed in Section 4, Education and Outreach, because it crosses both the Science and the Education and Outreach portfolios.

We have conducted several activities in 2012 to further our four targeted initiatives:

- We supported a Catalysis Meeting titled “K-12 Evolution Education and the Underserved,” which met to examine how K-12 education reform in evolutionary science can (1) impact the major under-representation of ethnic minorities in evolutionary science, and (2) address the tendency of these groups to reject evolutionary science.
- We supported “Learning Evolution from the Fossil Record,” a working group to design and deliver innovative programming that uses fossils to engage students in explorations of evolutionary concepts.
- In evolutionary medicine, a working group entitled “The evolution of virulence in a human infectious disease: the case study of HIV” will combine large-scale data analysis and mathematical modeling to address the past and potential future trends of HIV virulence.
- We have two working groups focused on designing curricula to infuse medical education with evolutionary thinking. This includes a working group composed of interdisciplinary, international, and intergenerational group of

physicians, scientists, educators, and students to define core competencies in evolutionary biology for physicians and other health professionals, design model curricula and learning experiences that can advance evolutionary education for health professionals, and provide open access to these resources and disseminate them.

- A Catalysis Meeting entitled “The Perils of Being Bipedal: an Evolutionary Perspective on Human Musculoskeletal Disorders” was held in March 2012. This received news coverage in Science (sciencemag.org/content/336/6084/974.full).
- A Catalysis Meeting entitled “Evolution of Human Teeth and Jaws: Implications for Dentistry and Orthodontics” was also held in March, and has already yielded a publication in Evolution Anthropology and garnered press in Science (sciencemag.org/content/336/6084/973.full).
- A Catalysis Meeting entitled “Ecological Models and Social Networks: How evolutionary forces shape networks and communities,” a two-part conference to explore linking evolutionary processes as causal mechanisms for change in social networks.
- Our current round of proposals included several that our Advisory Board has recommended for support and that will address themes in our targeted initiatives; (1) a Catalysis Meeting entitled “Synthesizing the Evolutionary and Social Sciences Approaches to Human Cooperation” was submitted in response to our “Evolution and the Social Sciences” initiative, (2) a sabbatical project proposed by a faculty member at Spelman College (an HBCU) will develop teaching modules aimed at conveying evolutionary science to women of under-represented minorities, and (3) a Working Group entitled “Genetics and Genealogy: Teaching Evolution and Human Diversity to Middle School” was submitted in response to our “K-12 Education for Under-represented Minorities” initiative.

The NESCent Postdoctoral Fellowship Program is training the next generation of data scientists. Meet recent fellows at nescent.org/science/postdoctoral.

We have also capitalized on our intensive assessment of the processes that ensure that Working Groups and Catalysis Meetings are successful in terms of stimulating collaboration and producing synthesis. Craig McClain, our Assistant Director of Science, is now a certified meeting facilitator, and has actively engaged with several groups that self-identified as needing help gaining productive momentum, or that NESCent identified as needing help. These interventions appear to have been successful in boosting productivity in these groups, but we will need another year to fully assess their effects. We have also developed a new, more detailed Best Practices document (building from our existing document) that is provided to all group leaders, with encouragement to seek assistance and input on planning and running meetings.

2.22013 PLANS

Given that our funding from the National Science Foundation will end formally in December 2014, and in the absence of any confirmation of continued funding (from federal or other sources), we will be ending calls for proposals

for our postdoctoral fellowships and our working group meetings. The last postdoctoral fellowship proposal round was in July 2012, and the last proposal round for working groups will be in December 2012.

Despite this plan, we anticipate a lively continuation of already-confirmed Working Groups and Catalysis Meetings in 2013. We had an extraordinarily strong round of proposals in the second half of 2012, and our Advisory Board members recommended supporting six Catalysis Meetings and four Working Group proposals from this round alone. From the perspective of the quality and quantity of proposals we are receiving, NESCent is gaining momentum and is poised to support increasingly high quality work in the last two years of our core funding. Our in-house community of scientists during 2012-2013 will consist of 4-5 sabbatical scholars, 13 postdocs, and an exciting mix of short-term visitors and graduate student fellows. We also received supplemental funding for two important meetings in 2013:

1. A meeting on evolutionary developmental biology, entitled “The Shape of the Future: A Workshop To Consolidate and Advance the Field of Evolutionary Developmental Biology.” Cassandra Extavour of Harvard University is the principal organizer of this meeting, which aims to reflect on the achievements of the field of evo-devo, and the new directions that the field can take, given the technological advances that are available or emerging.
2. A second meeting to support the career development of women in the biological sciences, entitled “Women Evolving Biological Sciences” (organizers: Claire Horner-Devine and Joyce Yen of the University of Washington, and Samantha Forde of the University of California at Santa Cruz). An earlier meeting was also held at NESCent as a hosted event in 2011, and featured presentations by senior women academics, as well as networking activities. Participants were enthusiastic and offered high praise for the meeting and its outcomes.

3. INFORMATICS

NESCent continues to have a vibrant informatics program that enables sponsored science projects as well as serving as an incubator for sustainable, community-driven cyberinfrastructure.

3.1 2012 ACTIVITIES

3.1.1 SUPPORT FOR SPONSORED SCIENCE

NESCent continues to support the informatics needs of sponsored science through a standard suite of services for online collaboration, high-performance computing, videoconferencing, as well as custom support for projects that require it. The standard support infrastructure was upgraded with the addition of four High Performance Computing nodes on the Duke Shared Cluster Resource Cluster, each with 128GB of memory and four 8-core CPUs. This brings our high-priority share on the cluster to a total of 27 nodes with 424 CPU cores, 224 on nodes with 96GB or more of shared memory, as required by the memory-intensive and multi-threaded applications that several of our sponsored scientists have been developing. The DSCR remains an important resource for resident and visiting scientists alike.

New custom projects include support for the Working Group “Synthesizing and databasing fossil calibrations: divergence dating and beyond” (PIs: Daniel Ksepka of North Carolina State University and James Parham of the

University of Alabama), which has the aim of providing a publication route for standardized data on fossil specimen ages and phylogenetic placements in order to improve molecular divergence time calibration. NESCent is working with the group to develop a special data publication track in Palaeontologia Electronica with an associated online database.

The Working Group titled “HIP: Hackathons, Interoperability, Phylogenies” (PIs: Rutger Vos of the University of Reading, Arlin Stoltzfus of the Center for Advanced Research in Biotechnology, and Enrico Pontelli of New Mexico State University) organized a highly successful hackathon at NESCent in June focused on web services for delivering Tree of Life information from producers to users. Four NESCent staff participated in the hackathon; two have served on the leadership team (Lapp and Cranston), and a graduate student research assistant has been recruited to provide continuity of software development between hackathons, of which there are two more planned (at iPlant and BioSync).

Instead of a lab or field research model, NESCent is what the U.S. National Science Foundation calls a “synthesis center,” which means it focuses on re-using existing data to address “big picture” questions. To that end, NESCent is a key partner in a number of digital data initiatives aimed at removing barriers to accessing, sharing and interpreting data from diverse sources. Read on for examples of what NESCent is doing to help researchers from across the globe get a grip on their data.

The need to collaboratively compile trait data from many different species is common to several different NESCent sponsored science projects. NESCent has been working to customize the existing open source data curation software mx (mx.phenomix.org) for use by multiple groups, including:

- “The tree of sex – a comprehensive synthesis of sex determination systems in eukaryotes” (PIs: Doris Bachtrog, Judith Mank and Catherine Peichel), which is testing for patterns in traits relevant to sex determination across the tree of life.
- “Large-scale demographic, network and behavioral trait analyses of sociality” (PIs: Dustin Rubenstein, James Hunt, Jennifer Fewell), which aims to do data-driven discovery of patterns in social attributes across the diversity of group-living taxa.
- “Evolutionary shifts in vertebrate visual ecology and visual system morphology” (PIs: Margaret Hall, Christopher Heesy, Andrew Iwaniuk), which aims to study how the structure of the vertebrate visual system varies with activity pattern, sensitivity, acuity and other factors by looking at phylogenetic patterns across taxa.

NESCent also provides custom support to individual resident scientists, such as sabbatical scholar Michael Wade of Indiana University, who came to NESCent in possession of the raw data from the classic mid-20th century Tribolium

competition experiments of his late PhD advisor, Thomas Park. Summary results from these experiments are shown as figures in most introductory ecology textbooks, yet the original data has never before been available in digital form. It is estimated that there are 660,000 lines of data, all handwritten in pencil on immaculately organized 3-ring binder pages. To preserve, share, and allow repurposing of these data, the pages have been scanned in partnership with the Duke Libraries, and NESCent is transcribing the data through a commercial crowdsourcing approach (Amazon Mechanical Turk). The results are being incorporated into new curriculum materials to be disseminated through an educational partnership between the Dryad Digital Repository and Understanding Evolution (based at U. California Berkeley). This will enable teachers to bring the data into their classrooms for lessons about competition between species while at the same time teaching students about experimental design and the value of data preservation.

For the project “Seeing is believing: Creating 3D environments to facilitate evolutionary education”, short-term visitor Corey Hart had developed a natural selection teaching tool in which plant and animal species interact in an immersive virtual 3D world. NESCent helped Dr. Hart submit a successful grant proposal to Amazon for use of commercial cloud computing resources; we then collaborated with Dr. Hart to implement his tool within the OpenSim framework both on Amazon’s EC2 cloud service and on virtual machines hosted locally.

3.1.2 INFORMATICS TRAINING AND OUTREACH

For the 6th year in a row, NESCent served as a mentoring organization in the Google Summer of Code. Google provided funding for eight students to work remotely with mentors over the summer on open-source, collaborative software development projects ranging from building tool support for minimum information standards in phylogenetics, to platform-independent visualization of dynamic phylogeographical patterns (for details of each project, see informatics.nescent.org/wiki/Phyloinformatics_Summer_of_Code_2012). Additionally, researchers Jane Greenberg (University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill) and Heather Piwowar (NESCent) were co-mentors for two summer internships (notebooks.dataone.org/) supported through DataONE.

The 3rd Conference on Informatics for Phylogenetics, Evolution, and Biodiversity (iEvoBio) was held in July Ottawa, ON, in coordination with 2012 Evolution Meetings. The conference, which had over 150 registrants this year, promotes collaborative, open-source software and standards development in the fields of evolution and biodiversity. NESCent Assistant Director for Informatics Hilmar Lapp served as chair of the organizing committee, and NESCent continues to provide some sponsorship (with a regularly declining contribution each year). In addition to its innovative programming (such as lightning talks, and birds-of-a-feather sessions, and a challenge competition), the conference now offers graduate student travel fellowships and a mentoring program.

3.1.3 CROSS-CENTER COORDINATION

NESCent participated in June in a cross-center National Science Foundation workshop at SESYNC entitled “BIO Centers and Center-like activities Awardee Meeting on Cyberinfrastructure.” The workshop led to NESCent’s subsequent participation as a collaborator in two successful cross-center CI supplemental awards: “Materials and Workshops for Cyberinfrastructure Education in Biology” (led by BEACON), and a “Cyberinfrastructure Information Exchange and Cyber Challenges Working Group” (led by SESYNC).

Allen Rodrigo represented NESCent at a US-European Union workshop

organized by the National Science Foundation and the EU Science Foundation to discuss opportunities to develop shared cyberinfrastructure and resources for data sharing (marum.de/Page12529.html). NESCent is presently part of a US proposal (led by the National Ecological Observatory Network) to develop these trans-Atlantic collaborations.

3.1.4 EXTERNALLY-FUNDED PROJECTS

The core National Science Foundation funding to NESCent enables the center to initiate or participate in a number of externally funded cyberinfrastructure projects that are aligned with the center’s mission. Some of these grow out of sponsored science projects while others have the aim of improving the capacity for synthetic evolutionary science more generally.

PUBLISH AND PRESERVE YOUR DATA IN THE DRYAD DIGITAL DATA REPOSITORY

A digital data repository known as Dryad aims to provide secure and permanent access to data in biology and the earth sciences. Incubated at NESCent five years ago, Dryad contains data from thousands of articles and authors from over 150 different journals in biology and medicine. Dryad has grown significantly in importance in the past year as a trusted home for the long tail of data underlying scientific articles, and has cemented partnerships with some major new journals and publishers (blog.datadryad.org/2012/06/15/). A major new National Science Foundation award for further development of Dryad started in April 2012 (DBI-1147166). The award provides \$2.4M over four years to improve backend processes that would support an order of magnitude scale-up in the rate of deposit, a much wider diversity of journals and submission integration processes, and implement a sustainable business model. Partners on the grant include NESCent (through Duke U.), the UNC School of Information and Library Sciences and the NC State University Digital Libraries. In July, Dryad was incorporated as an independent not-for-profit organization, and the first meeting of its Board of Directors was held at NESCent. A workshop was held at the center in December 2011 to develop educational modules for college and graduate students based on Dryad data, called DryadLab, as a collaboration between NESCent’s EOC group, Dryad, and Understanding Evolution (UC Berkeley). The first modules, which are currently in testing by the Understanding Evolution Teacher Advisory Committee, were introduced at the SSE Education Symposium “Teaching with data: Opportunities to engage students in doing science” in July 2012 in Ottawa.

BUILDING A GLOBAL DIGITAL DATA NETWORK FOR BIOLOGY AND THE EARTH SCIENCES

NESCent is one of the lead partner organizations in the Data Observation Network for Earth (DataONE), a National Science Foundation OCI-funded virtual network of data repositories and registries in environmental science, ecology, and evolution. The first release of DataONE’s online presence was officially launched in July, and Dryad is among the first member nodes (repositories that take advantage of DataONE’s discovery and preservation infrastructure).

ASSEMBLING THE TREE OF LIFE FOR ALL 2M NAMED SPECIES

Karen Cranston of NESCent is the Principal Investigator of a new National Science Foundation Assembling, Visualizing and Analysing the Tree of Life (AVAToL) program award: “Collaborative Research: Automated and community-driven synthesis of the tree of life”. This is a three-year, \$5.76M grant to a team of researchers from ten universities to create the first comprehensive draft tree of life by synthesizing existing phylogenetic and taxonomic knowledge, and to build tools that will enable the community to improve, annotate, and expand this tree into the future.

Taking Darwin Day on the road: The Darwin Day Roadshow connects scientists and students in classrooms across the country.

MEASURING SCHOLARLY IMPACT BEYOND THE LIBRARY AND THE LAB

NESCent and DataONE postdoc Heather Piwowar received a \$125K award from the Sloan foundation for further development of a site that aggregates and displays the online conversation around research products including articles, datasets, and grey literature, with the aim of supporting broad, ground-up adoption of a more inclusive understanding and assessment (impactstory.org/).

OTHER PROJECTS

Another not-for-profit incubated at the center is the Phyloinformatics Research Foundation (PRF), which held its second board meeting at NESCent in December 2011. The PRF provides strategic direction to projects under its umbrella, currently TreeBase and the Tree of Life Web.

NESCent continues to promote the Generic Model Organism Database (GMOD) project, the distributed, open-source genome informatics community behind the widely-used GMOD software suite. A community support specialist (Amelia Ireland) was hired in July 2012 through an NIH award to the University of California at Berkeley. Her charge is to keep the community healthy and growing through organizing annual GMOD meetings and courses, providing training workshops at conferences, curating online documentation and tutorials, overseeing help and feature request traffic on the project mailing lists, and related activities (gmod.org/wiki/GMOD_Community_Support).

This year saw the first public release of the Phenoscope Knowledgebase, which aims to demonstrate the potential of synthesizing phenotypic information across diverse systematic and genetic studies using semantic technologies (kb.phenoscape.org).

The center continued its role as a host to informatics-related meetings from externally-funded projects, some of which have been incubated at the center:

- A Mammalian Feeding Ontology Workshop in May 2012, sponsored by an independent project that grew out of a NESCent working group: “ABI Innovation: A novel database and ontology for evolutionary analyses of mammalian feeding physiology” (DBI-1062333)
- The 2nd annual summit meeting of the National Science Foundation-funded Phenotype Research Coordination Network (phenotypernc.org) was held at NESCent in February 2012, with 61 participants in attendance.

3.2 PLANS FOR 2013

In the coming year, while continuing our core functions, we will be focusing special attention on three areas:

- We will be using the informatics projects at the center to a greater extent as training opportunities for local undergraduate and graduate students from a variety of academic programs (e.g. biology, computer science, information science).
- We will scale up our efforts to work with our sponsored scientists in securing institutional homes and external support, where needed, for ongoing informatics activities on projects that were begun with NESCent support.
- We will increase the proportion of NESCent’s informatics program oriented toward externally-funded projects in support of sustainable community resources. Among the exciting milestones in the coming year will be the first release of a synthetic Tree of Life from the AVAToL Open Tree of Life project.

4. EDUCATION AND OUTREACH

NESCent’s Year 8 Education and Outreach activities once again reflect a successful blending of established programs with several new initiatives. Both the new and existing activities fit within the framework of what have become the five pillars of NESCent Education/Outreach:

- Outreach to the Education Community
- Outreach to the General Public
- Outreach to Underrepresented Minorities
- Outreach to International Science and Education Communities
- “Inreach” to the Science Community

4.1 2012 ACTIVITIES

4.1.1 OUTREACH TO THE EDUCATION COMMUNITY

NESCent’s Darwin Day Roadshow (roadshow.nescent.org) program once again sent teams of NESCent scientists/educators to K-12 institutions in small, rural communities around the country to celebrate Charles Darwin’s birthday with talks about evolution research being conducted at NESCent, and about careers in science. In only its second year, the program grew significantly, receiving over 100 applications from 27 states. This year, 10 NESCent scientists/educators visited schools in Oregon, Washington, Arkansas, Missouri, Louisiana and West Virginia.

DR. JOHN HAWKS, UNIVERSITY OF WISCONSIN, SPEAKER IN THE 2011 NABT EVOLUTION SYMPOSIUM

In partnership with AIBS, our annual Evolution Symposium was organized as part of the National Association of Biology Teachers (NABT) annual conference. Entitled “Changing Humans in a Changing Environment” it featured four internationally known researchers in human evolution and evolutionary anthropology, and was once again accessible via live webcast. We developed, produced and distributed a CD ROM of learning resources and offered a half day, hands on teacher workshop to compliment the symposium.

We once again delivered our annual three day summer workshop for high school instructors (this year, delivered in conjunction with our sponsorship of a Kenan Fellow – see “New Initiatives”), as well as multiple other workshops, short talks and presentations for high school teachers on effective strategies for teaching evolution.

Our successful “Evolution in the News” feature and podcast series, in partnership with the Understanding Evolution website, continued and was translated into Spanish (see “New Initiatives”). We also continued to support a working group led by Drs. Kathryn Perez and Rebecca Price entitled “EvoCI toolkit: concept inventories to assess conceptual understanding of evolution” which has been extraordinarily productive, with several papers published, in press or in preparation.

4.1.2 OUTREACH TO THE GENERAL PUBLIC

The highlight of our outreach efforts for the general public continued to be the annual Darwin Day event we cofounded and co-sponsor with the North Carolina Museum of Natural Sciences. This day-long event attracted several thousand visitors to the museum on Feb. 11th, 2012. NESCent hosted the keynote speaker (Dr. Roland Kays, NC Nature Research Center) and ran several interactive stations and booths. NESCent also sponsored or co-sponsored several other evolution-related talks for the general public, many in partnership with the NC Museum of Natural Sciences.

4.1.3 OUTREACH TO UNDERREPRESENTED MINORITIES

We continued to organize and run a collection of evolution outreach activities at the annual meeting of the Society for the Advancement of Chicanos and Native Americans in Science (SACNAS). “Evolution and Ecology at SACNAS” has been run for several years at the conference, and NESCent continues to be the primary organizer of these events, with co-sponsorship from NCEAS, NIMBioS, SSE, ESA and AIBS. As always, NESCent postdocs were involved as symposium speakers and mentors to minority undergraduates attending the conference.

We once again collaborated with Scott Edwards of Harvard University and Rich Kliman of Cedar Crest College on the Undergraduate Diversity at Evolution program, which sends undergraduates to the annual Evolution (SSE/SSB/ASN) conference and provides them with mentoring and professional development while there. This year, NESCent assumed full financial responsibility and organizational oversight for the program, which brought 18 undergraduates (most of them from underrepresented minority groups) to Ottawa, Ontario, Canada for a meeting that also included the Canadian and European evolutionary biology societies.

We continued the NESCent MSI Faculty Travel Award program as well, by sending a faculty member from a minority-serving institution (Dr. Michèle Nishiguchi, from New Mexico State University) to the Evolution 2012 Conference in Ottawa to present original research, and to mentor diverse undergraduates.

NESCent’s Seeing and Learning Science Afterschool (SALSA) program continued and expanded. This program was developed by a team consisting of Dr. Rafa Rubio de Casas (former NESCent postdoc), Sarah Cohn (undergraduate intern from Univ. of North Carolina) and Jory Weintraub (NESCent Asst. Director of Education/Outreach). The program visits after-school programs – primarily serving underrepresented minority students – to teach students basic concepts in evolutionary biology through engaging, hands-on activities. SALSA was run at programs serving primarily Hispanic and African American students, as well as a sizable population of Karen (Myanmar) refugees. Workshops were delivered in both English and Spanish.

Eleven travel awards were given to students from underrepresented minority groups to participate in short courses and workshops offered by the NESCent Academy (see “Inreach” section). Additionally, as part of our targeted initiative for evolution education programs focused on underrepresented minorities at the K-12 level, we supported a catalysis meeting titled “Using genetics and genealogy to teach evolution and human diversity,” led by Drs. Nina Jablonski, Mark Shriver and Henry Gates, as well as a working group titled “Learning evolution from the fossil record: K-12 explorations in deep time,” led by Drs. Dena Smith, Roy Plotnick, Margaret Yacobucci and Pedro Marengo. We have received several additional strong proposals in our most recent round as a

NESCENT CONTINUES TO ORGANIZE AND RUN A VARIETY OF EVOLUTION OUTREACH ACTIVITIES FOR UNDERREPRESENTED MINORITIES

result of this targeted request for proposals, and will be reviewing those at our upcoming board meeting, so we consider this to be a very successful effort to support K-12 evolution education for underrepresented minorities.

4.1.4 OUTREACH TO INTERNATIONAL SCIENCE AND EDUCATION COMMUNITIES

The NESCent Ambassador program (ambassadors.nescent.org) grew and expanded, with several new or continuing international programs that included:

- The Caribbean – A team of four NESCent scientists/educators and collaborator Elvis Nuñez from the University of Florida traveled to Jamaica, Trinidad, Barbados and Belize to deliver workshops on evolutionary science and evolution education to students and instructors at both K-12 and undergraduate institutions.
- Kenya – A team of four NESCent ambassadors conducted a two-week workshop on computational phyloinformatics at the Kenya Medical Research Institute (KEMRI), run by the Wellcome Trust in Kilifi, Kenya.
- Galapagos – A team of three NESCent ambassadors conducted a series of evolution education/outreach workshops for elementary school students and teachers, as well as Galapagos naturalist guides, on the islands of Santa Cruz and San Cristobal.
- Bali – For the second year in a row, NESCent ambassadors conducted a two-week workshop on phylogenetic inference for Indonesian scientists and graduate students at the Indonesian Biodiversity Research Center.

These ambassadorships not only increase our international presence and provide valuable scientific training and expertise around the world, but also serve as unique professional development opportunities for NESCent scientists. (Each ambassadorship involves at least one NESCent postdoctoral fellow, in addition to senior NESCent scientists/education staff.)

4.1.5 “INREACH” TO THE SCIENCE COMMUNITY

Three new courses and two pre-existing course were offered this summer through the NESCent Academy (academy.nescent.org).

- Next-generation Sequencing in Evolutionary Biology (June 11-19, 2012): An introduction to issues in the handling of next-gen sequencing data for metagenomic studies, phylogeny reconstruction and comparative analyses of gene expression. Amazon Web Services and BioMatters, Ltd. both donated resources for use by course participants. 112 applications were received and the course had 26 participants (two international). Six travel awards were given to under-represented minority participants.
- Evolutionary Quantitative Genetics (August 6-11, 2012): An introduction to evolutionary quantitative genetic theory, and to building and testing evolutionary models. Cosponsored by the American Society of Naturalists. Thirty-eight applications were received and the course had 23 participants (six international). Four travel awards were given to under-represented minority participants.
- Anatomy Ontologies in Evolutionary Biology and Genetics (July 30 – August 3, 2012): An introduction to ontology design principles and practices for interoperability of anatomical information across evolutionarily disparate taxa. Cosponsored by Phenotype Ontology RCN and the National Center for Biomedical Ontology. Thirteen applications were received (two from international applicants) and all 13 were selected for participation in this course. One travel award from NESCent and three from the Phenotype RCN grant were awarded to under-represented minority participants.
- Computational Phyloinformatics (August 5-18, 2012): A hands-on course in building large-scale phylogenetic pipelines, post-tree analyses, handling very large trees and large collections of trees, in Perl, Ruby, and SQL. The course was held at Moscow State University, cosponsored by the Russian Academy of Sciences and the Phyloinformatics Research Foundation.

- Evolutionary Medicine at Mount Desert Island Biodiversity Center (August 6-10, 2012): The Mount Desert Island Biological Laboratory offered a course in Evolution and Medicine aimed at physicians and researchers. We co-sponsored this course as part of our evolutionary medicine theme.

Additionally, NESCent hosted the externally funded GMOD Summer School (gmod.org/wiki/2012_GMOD_Summer_School).

We continued to organize and conduct a weekly seminar series for in house scientists and invited speakers from the local Triangle area in North Carolina. We also continued the “NESCent Director’s Seminar Series” to bring in more diverse speakers from outside the Triangle area to NESCent. This year’s speakers included Dr. Lisa Matisoo Smith (University of Otago, New Zealand), Dr. Keith Crandall (Brigham Young University/George Washington University), Dr. Michael R. Rose (University of California, Irvine), and Dr. Joseph Heitman (Duke University).

Finally, we received nearly 20 entries for the second annual “NESCent Evolution Video Contest”, which was held at the Evolution Societies meeting in Ottawa, Ontario, Canada to a packed auditorium of over 250 attendees. The winners were “The evolution of an alternative male mating strategy: socializing with less attractive rivals,” submitted by Cedric Tan and colleagues of the Edward Grey Institute of Field Ornithology (1st place), and “Lessons from Evolution: Dating with Darwin,” submitted by Megan Head and Amber Teacher of the University of Exeter (2nd place). These videos, as well as all of the others submitted for this year’s film festival can be viewed at filmfestival.nescent.org/2012-entries/.

4.1.6 NEW INITIATIVES AND ACTIVITIES

Several new initiatives and activities highlighted our education/outreach efforts over the past year, including:

- NABT Travel Award – NESCent introduced a new travel award to send one enthusiastic, motivated instructor from the high school level and another from a community college to attend the annual conference of the National Association of Biology Teachers (NABT). These individuals, designated “NESCent Evolution Scholars,” attend the conference (including NESCent’s annual NABT Evolution Symposium) and then return to their campuses to develop new activities and curricular materials based on the evolutionary knowledge they acquire at the conference. They are also expected to lead professional development activities for their colleagues at their home institutions, during which they share information and resources collected at the conference. We received 66 applications from around the country. The travel award winners were Jaime Sabel (Kirkwood Community College in Iowa City, IA) and Barry Greenwald (Harding High School in St. Paul, MN).
- NABT Evolution Education Award – NESCent has taken over sponsorship of this annual award (in partnership with the Biological Sciences Curriculum Study – BSCS). This year’s winner is Dr. James Krupa from the University of Kentucky.
- NESCent also established a partnership/collaboration with BEACON – The Center for the Study of Evolution in Action – to help organize/conduct the annual NABT Evolution Symposium, in conjunction with NESCent and AIBS.
- For the first time, NESCent sponsored a Kenan Fellow – a talented high school biology teacher (Robin Bulleri, Carrboro High School, Carrboro, NC) who is spending this year working with NESCent under the mentorship of both Jory Weintraub (NESCent Asst. Director of Education/Outreach) and Dr. Paul Harnik (NESCent Postdoc). Ms. Bulleri played an integral role in organizing and conducting NESCent’s summer workshop for high school teachers (with Dr. Weintraub), and worked on a synthetic research project (with Dr. Harnik).
- As mentioned previously, NESCent played a vastly expanded role in the planning, organization and funding of the Undergrad Diversity at Evolution program, which brings diverse undergrads to the annual evolution conference.

4.2 PLANS FOR 2013

In the next year, NESCent’s Seeing and Learning Science Afterschool (SALSA) program will expand to a local after-school program that has a sizable population of Korean students. NESCent postdoc Mira Han will be working with NESCent’s education/outreach group to deliver educational workshops in Korean.

NESCent’s long-standing Evolution In The News program received a mini-grant from the European Society of Evolutionary Biology to translate its web-based stories into Spanish. That translation will be completed shortly, and in the coming year the Spanish versions of these stories will be promoted widely as part of our minority outreach efforts.

We are also developing ideas for a program partnering NESCent postdocs with minority-serving institution (MSI) faculty to increase research capacity at MSIs and expand professional development for NESCent postdocs. In addition, we’re exploring ways to expand our summer workshop for teachers to become a traveling program that would train high school teachers across the state of North Carolina in evolution education.

5. COMMUNICATIONS

Calls for better science communication are especially critical in the face of misinformation about evolutionary science, and in light of ongoing attacks on evolution education. To that end, NESCent continues to produce a regular stream of news in evolutionary science for use by the media. In the past year we wrote and distributed nearly twenty news releases highlighting major results from NESCent-sponsored projects, on topics ranging from the health consequences of cousin marriage, to the origins of insect hearing, to what happens when a deadly bird parasite switches hosts.

Reporters receive these releases through an online news service sponsored by the American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS). For a chronological list of these news releases please visit nescent.org/news/News_releases.php.

5.1 2012 ACTIVITIES

Overall, NESCent news releases for the 2011-2012 reporting year received more than 52,000 page views by registered reporters and journalists, up from 32,000 page views for last year. Issuing a press release doesn’t guarantee news coverage, but it does guarantee that journalists will consider scientific studies they wouldn’t have spotted otherwise, due to limited time and lack of access to academic journals.

The strategy seems to be working. The number of stories in the mainstream media resulting from NESCent news releases has gone up by about 50% each year, whether the stories take the form of newspaper and magazine articles, television shows, radio interviews, podcasts or blogs. NESCent-sponsored science appeared in approximately 40 mainstream media stories in reporting year 2009-2010, 65 media stories in 2010-2011, and nearly 100 stories in 2011-2012 – including outlets such as Science Magazine, NPR, Scientific American, Discovery Channel, Wired, The New York Times, and TIME Magazine.

The benefits of media outreach in terms of enhanced readership and visibility for scientists are real. When NESCent scientist Julie Meachen published a recent study in the journal PLoS ONE, for example, her journal article received over 1600 views in the first month after publication. But the number of readers of the first lay translation of her work – i.e., the press release – was fourfold higher. After just one month, Meachen’s press release received nearly 6000 views, and by the fourth month that number had shot up to over 7175. What’s more, these numbers are just for the news release. What they don’t reflect are the numbers of readers of the stories that came afterward in major media outlets. As a result of our press release, Meachen’s paper was later featured in Science Magazine, Discover Magazine, and MSNBC News, among others. Collectively these outlets reach hundreds of thousands of readers each month – a readership that no academic journal could achieve.

In addition to gaining news coverage for NESCent-sponsored science, we also organized several outreach events that received local or national media attention, including hosting a teacher leadership program called the Kenan Fellows Program for Curriculum and Leadership Development, which was featured in the Durham Herald-Sun, and our second annual Darwin Day Roadshow, which was featured in US News and World Report.

NESCent runs a journalist-in-residence program as well. The program offers a unique opportunity for reporters, producers, and editors to work on an ambitious, exciting project of their own choosing with an evolutionary focus.

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Fellowships are open to salaried or freelance journalists in print, electronic or broadcast media. Journalists of all nationalities are welcome to apply. Proposals are considered twice a year, with deadlines on January 15 and July 10. We recruited and hosted two journalists in this reporting period: freelance journalist Michael Martin, who joined us for the month of October; and award-winning essayist and journalist Ilan Greenberg, who joined us for two months starting in November. Michael’s report on the life and work of evolutionary biologist Margie Profet was covered by the New York Times and Psychology Today. The coverage had unforeseen benefits. At the time that Michael published his articles, Dr. Profet’s whereabouts were unknown, even to her family. However, after the publication of Michael’s article, Dr. Profet was reunited with her family in May this year.

NESCent also sponsors a blog contest and conference travel fellowship for evolutionary bloggers. To apply for the award, writers are required to submit a blog post that highlights current or emerging evolutionary research. Winners receive \$750 apiece to cover travel and lodging expenses to attend ScienceOnline, a science communication conference held each January in North Carolina. In 2012, the winners were Catherine Pratt from Brown University, writing about the Trouble with Teeth (katiephd.com/the-trouble-with-teeth%E2%80%A6/), and Sarah Seiter of The University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill on Zombie Butterflies (butterfliesandscience.wordpress.com/2011/09/15/zombie-caterpillars-lurch-through-forest-canopy-infecting-their-brethren/).

5.2 PLANS FOR 2013

In October 2012, NESCent’s three partner institutions – Duke, UNC Chapel Hill, and NC State – jointly hosted a national science journalism conference on NC State’s Centennial Campus in Raleigh. NESCent is a member of the organizational team for the conference, which brought more than 500 leading science journalists, authors and bloggers to North Carolina to learn about breaking science news across various fields, including evolution. Learn more about the meeting at sciencewriters2012.org/.

Finally, in early 2013, NESCent will host a catalysis meeting aimed at improving media coverage of scientific topics that often find themselves at the center of social controversies, such as evolution, stem cells, and climate change. Titled “Reporting across the culture wars: Engaging media on evolution,” (Pls: John Logsdon and Lauri Lebo), the meeting will bring together scientists and journalists to brainstorm ways to ensure that researchers are better prepared to support accurate media coverage, and reporters and editors have a general understanding of scientific issues before public controversies erupt.

6. ASSESSMENT

NESCent’s assessment program seeks to evaluate whether we are fulfilling our mission and core values. NESCent’s mission is to “promote the synthesis of information, concepts and knowledge to address significant, emerging, or novel questions in evolutionary science and its applications. NESCent achieves this by supporting research and education across disciplinary, institutional, geographic, and demographic boundaries.” Specifically, we apply a three-tier evaluative system focused on people, products, and process. We seek to determine whether

- People: NESCent supports research and education across disciplinary, institutional, geographic, and demographic boundaries.
- Products: NESCent scientists are addressing questions that are significant, emerging, and/or novel in evolutionary science.
- Process: NESCent accomplishes (2) by promoting the synthesis of information, concepts and knowledge both within and beyond direct center activities.

6.1 2012 ACTIVITIES

6.1.1 ONGOING ACTIVITIES

NESCent’s assessment program continues to mature with the center. In this last year we have built on the cohesive assessment program across our three divisions established in 2011. This included both developing an assessment strategy and identifying specific data and analyses to meet our assessment objectives. As we seek funding for continued sustainability of our center we have added to our assessment objectives, and now include analyses and data relevant for potential funders.

Over the last year we have completed the transition of most of our Tier 1 assessment into an automated and replicable process. We now have a set of stock queries through Crystal Reports that can quickly query our internal NESCent Administrative Database (NEAD) and provide metrics on a wide variety of center activities including demographics and proposal counts. Briefly, NEAD serves as the backbone for all the center’s evaluative activities. Its strength rests on data entry by multiple users, from center Directors and administrative staff to individual participants in NESCent activities. Virtually every aspect of NESCent’s day-to-day operations, e.g. meeting registration, proposal process, and updating the website, require the use of our web-based interface of NEAD. This ensures that we accurately collect a wide range of data needed for assessment activities with an automated process. The importance of automated reports from NEAD cannot be underplayed as this has reduced staff time for report generation from a few weeks to a few hours.

For Tier 2 assessment in Year 8, we continue to focus on building accurate records of publications and grants resulting from NESCent activities. By establishing this record, we are now able to easily produce up-to-date estimates of the number of publications and citations. We are also measuring altmetrics for NESCent publications, including the number of online views and downloads, mentions in social media, and bookmarks on Zotero and Mendeley; these provide a more immediate and more multifaceted view of NESCent’s impact than citations alone. This work is now supported through our Sloan Foundation funding for ImpactStory (see 3.1.4)

With a newly acquired graduate student (Laura Sheble) from the School of Library and Information Science at UNC-Chapel Hill, we are also expanding our Tier 2 analyses. These new sets of analyses seek to address “What are the benefits of sustaining organizations such as NESCent?” and “What is the trajectory of knowledge accumulation at NESCent and how much broader increases in knowledge can be attributed to NESCent?”

Our assessment team is also actively collaborating with an assessment working group (Advancing Theory and Research on Scientific Synthesis; PIs John Parker and Ed Hackett) jointly funded by NCEAS and NESCent. The group draws together scientists who lead and conduct synthetic research with a diverse group of experts on scientific collaboration and research evaluation. The aim is to advance understanding of synthesis and develop new approaches for investigating it empirically, longitudinally and comparatively. The group is currently working on mapping synthesis outcomes in relation to broader scientific and disciplinary areas. Through textual analyses, we will collect data from all abstracts from all articles from all journals in which NCEAS and NESCent participants have published (1991-present, as these are available in Web of Science). Furthermore, to look at career effects of collaboration we plan on gathering all abstracts from all articles in all the journals in which a select sample of NCEAS and NESCent participants published prior to their NCEAS and NESCent collaborations. Hypothesizing that those on the fringes of ecology and evolution or in other disciplines may be affected most strongly, we will identify NCEAS and NESCent participants from other disciplines, draw a stratified sample, identify the journals in which they published previously, and gather all abstracts for those journals from the same time frame.

As part of Tier 3 assessment led by Jonathon Cummings (Associate Professor of Management, Fuqua School of Business, Duke University), the ‘Science of Science Project’ aims to improve the ways that NESCent promotes synthetic evolutionary science. The focus of the project is on the behaviors and attitudes of scientists towards collaboration, and how such behavior is changed as a result of NESCent support. In Year 8, we hired Samantha Thomas as a research analyst from the Master’s Program in Biostatistics (Duke School of Medicine). She has been instrumental in integrating the administrative data collected by NESCent with the survey data collected by Professor Cummings, and writing SAS scripts to analyze the data. Survey data is collected from working group participants

each time they meet at NESCent. For example, survey questions are asked about prior collaboration and participant expectations in the first meeting, methods of communication and satisfaction with how things are going in the second and third meetings, and whether their expectations were met in the fourth and final meeting. To date, survey data has been collected from 493 participants from 28 working groups for their first meeting, 334 participants from 23 working groups for their second meeting, 304 participants from 22 working groups for their third meeting, and 111 participants from 8 working groups for their fourth meeting. One goal for the upcoming year is to finish collecting survey data from participants as they finish up their four working group meetings.

Another goal for the upcoming year is to continue analyses of survey data collected from working groups. The data analyses so far have focused on the first three working group meetings, since there is comparatively less data on the fourth working group meeting. An interesting tension that has emerged from the data analyses involves working group size and amount of collaboration prior to meetings. Working groups vary in size from 11 to 34 (with a mean around 20), with presumably larger groups providing more perspectives to share among members. Prior collaboration is the extent to which participants reported collaborating with other working group members prior to a particular meeting (e.g., sharing data or writing a paper). A trend in the data so far has been that the larger the working group, the less likely participants collaborated together prior to the first meeting, the less likely participants collaborated together between the first and second meetings, and the less likely participants collaborated together between the second and third meetings. Thus, in larger groups, if fewer members collaborate together there may be missed opportunities for sharing diverse insight. Alternatively, participants may be taking advantage of division of labor to maximize where subsets of members can make a contribution. We plan to follow up these trends in the fourth meeting, as well as look at the relationship between group

Figure 6.3: A map of NESCent's disciplinary reach, produced in collaboration with Dr. Katy Börner

Figure 6.4: Cumulative new visitors per month

Figure 6.5: Percentage of professional stages participating in NESCent activities per year

size, level of collaboration, and outputs of the working group (e.g., publications, curriculum, grant proposals, software). It is also interesting that participants in relatively larger groups also report different reasons for joining: while it is more important for them that they can have a safe environment for sharing new ideas, to meet and network with people in their field, and to promote broad changes within their field, it is less important for participants in larger groups that they have the potential for manuscript publication, to advance a personal research program, or to create a new dataset, tool, or method. Regarding the amount of collaboration prior to meetings, it is also a strong positive predictor, in both the second and third meetings, of satisfaction with the working groups (e.g., level of task productivity by participants, quality of participant ideas and discussion). So while participants of larger groups may be collaborating less overall, those who do collaborate with a greater number of other participants report being more satisfied.

6.1.2 ASSESSMENT HIGHLIGHTS

In Year 8 we have so far produced 115 papers compared to the 89 papers from last year at this time. NESCent's h-index rose from 26 (2010) to 32 (2011) to our current h-index of 43. Our papers in the last year have garnered an additional 3,509 citations (Figure 1) for a cumulative total of 8,220 (an average of 17.53 and up from last years 16.13 citations per item).

We learned that when compared with most universities, regardless of how we define the comparison group, NESCent has a high citation per paper rate and a low percentage of uncited papers. We examined two sets of universities: 1) the top 40 universities in terms of R&D spending according to 2009 National Science Foundation data, and 2) a randomly-selected set of 120 colleges and universities. Funding data was retrieved from the WebCASPAR database. In

terms of publications per \$100,000 of funding, NESCent ranked 7th-highest among Top-40 universities and 38th-highest among the randomly-selected schools with 2.12 publications per \$100,000. When number of citations per \$10,000 was analyzed, NESCent ranked 10th among Top-40 universities and 22nd among the randomly-selected schools with an average of 2.07 citations per \$10,000. NESCent also had a low percent-uncited rate of 7.78%, which places the center 7th-lowest among the Top 40 universities.

Altmetrics demonstrate that NESCent's publications are attracting immediate attention and in ways not visible to citation counts alone. Articles have been bookmarked 753 times (up from 246 last year) in CiteULike, 6,842 times (up from 3,563) in Mendeley, mentioned 70 times in Wikipedia, and highlighted 26 times by Faculty of 1000.

The average number of authors on NESCent-related publications is greater during our second grant cycle than in our first. During the 2005-2009 the mean number of authors of papers 4.7 and increased to 5.3 in 2010-2011 (p=0.043). Although this is just a slight increase, it may signal an increase in collaborative networks formed by/at NESCent or signal a set projects that defined by broader more interdisciplinary science (Figure 2).

Over 40% of NESCent publications occur in high-impact journals (e.g., Nature, Science, Trends in Ecology and Evolution, Proceedings of the Royal Society B, Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, USA, Ecology Letters, Evolution, Systematic Biology, Genetics, American Naturalist).

With Katy Börner, we have updated the projection of NESCent related publications onto a map of science. Nodes on the map represent group of journals that forms disciplinary and subdisciplinary clusters (Fig. 3). These

clusters are based on a combination of the bibliographic coupling of references and keyword vectors. As expected, we have a strong representation in biological and evolutionary science journals (large green circles). In addition, the map illustrates NESCent's broad disciplinary reach ranging from the social sciences to math and physics. Of 554 subdisciplines and 13 disciplines in science, NESCent publications occur in 121 and 12 respectively.

NESCent continues to see an influx of new visitors into the center (Figure 4). The linear and steadily increasing line, with no sign of an asymptote, suggests we continued to draw new communities into NESCent. We also continue to maintain a 50:50 ratio of emerging to experienced scientists in NESCent activities (Figure 5).

6.2 PLANS FOR 2013

In 2013, our assessment program will continue to inform planning for the sustainability of the NESCent. We currently view our assessment program as having three main audiences including: our current funders (National Science Foundation), future funders of center activities, and our internal scientific and administrative communities, who use the results to improve NESCent's programs and operations. Thus our assessment program will focus on function, productivity, and marketability. We anticipate seeing the fruits of our long-term "Science of Science" program. Our continued collaborations with the "Advancing Theory and Research on Scientific Synthesis" Working group will allow us to add a disciplinary dimension to our understanding of how synthesis centers affect participating scientists. Another new direction will be to address how NESCent participation increases the likelihood of successful grant funding.

7. ADMINISTRATION

The primary focus of the past year's activities within the administration at NESCent have been to increase efficiency, by building better tools & processes as well increasing staff training opportunities.

7.1 2012 ACTIVITIES

In August, 2012 we lost our Assistant Director for Research Administration, Phillip Grosshans. Phillip moved on to take up a full-time and permanent position at another center at Duke University. Phillip joined NESCent in January 2011, and it is fair to say that he left an indelible impression on NESCent. We benefited from his years of experience at Duke's Office of Research Services, and his skill at navigating the complexities of NESCent's operations. He also helped NESCent establish links with the Office of Corporate and Foundation Relations at Duke, and he has helped formulate plans for NESCent's future. His cheerful presence will be missed, and we are very sorry to have lost a loyal, dedicated and enthusiastic member of staff.

On a positive note, we have been fortunate to recruit Catherine Craver to replace Phillip as the Assistant Director for Research Administration. Catherine has spent a great deal of time as an administrator at Duke, and also brings a wealth of experience in organizational best practice. Catherine began at NESCent in October 2012.

Todd Vision, Associate Director for Informatics, was on sabbatical from July 1, 2011 to June 30, 2012. During that time period, Hilmar Lapp served as Acting

Associate Director from July 1, 2011 to August 31, 2011, and Joel Kingsolver (Professor of Biology at UNC Chapel Hill and former Associate Director for Science), served as Acting Associate Director for Informatics from September 1, 2011 through June 2012. Also, Brian Wiegmann, Associate Director for Education and Outreach, was on sabbatical from July 1, 2012 to December 31, 2012. Dr. Jenny Xiang (Professor for Plant Biology at NCSU) is serving as Acting Associate Director during that time period.

Vladimir Gapeyev, Database Applications Analyst, left NESCent in April 2012, and Sandra Hall, User Interface Developer, left NESCent in July 2012. Again, we are sorry to lose two valuable members of the NESCent informatics team. A search is currently underway for new informatics staff.

We welcomed Jeff Sturkey to NESCent. Jeff, who was one of the center's earliest staff members. Sturkey rejoined NESCent as a Staff Specialist in April 2012, supporting the Education, Outreach and Communications group

Adriana Briscoe, Joe Graves, Ary Hoffman, Blaire van Valkenburgh and Marta Wayne left the NESCent Advisory Board. Rick Ree is now Chair, and Vicki Funk is Assoc. Chair. We have recruited Jeanne Cavender-Bares, Patricia Kelly, Carlo Maley, Monica Medina, and Susan Williams to the NAB, and they begin their term on December 1, 2012.

David Pfennig stepped down as the UNC-Chapel Hill representative from NESCent's Operations Committee and has been replaced by Dr. Maria Servedio.

For those who have left NESCent - Phillip, Vladimir, Sandra, Adriana, Joe, Marta, Ary, Blaire, Marta, and David - we want to place on record our sincere and deeply-felt gratitude for their service. For those who have joined NESCent - Catherine, Jeff, Jeanne, Patricia, Carlo, Monica, Susan and Maria - welcome.

The administrative team continued with the planning of the Evolution 2014 conference. To that end our logistics coordinators, Stephanie Risbon and Danielle Wilson, attended the Evolution 2012 conference in Ottawa, working with on-site committees and meeting with the conference organizers to gain a more complete understanding of the logistic and operational complexities of this particular conference.

7.2 PLANS FOR 2013

An area we plan to focus on is staff development. Whether or not NESCent continues beyond 2014, we need to make sure that our staff is well-trained and competitive. Consequently, we will continue to offer staff the opportunity to attend courses, workshops and training.

The second area that will occupy our time is the Evolution 2014 conference. At the start of the new year, we will begin to solidify our plans for the conference activities, develop the website, and finalize the logistics of the meeting.

8. EXTERNALLY FUNDED RESEARCH: NESCent Grants and Proposals

FUNDED: NESCENT-DUKE UNIVERSITY

TITLE	PI	FUNDING AGENCY	DATES	DIRECT	INDIRECT	TOTAL
PIRE: Understanding Marine Biodiversity Along Geographical and Anthropogenic Stress Gradients	Allen Rodrigo (Forrest Rohwer)	NSF (Subaward from San Diego State University)	1/1/2013 - 12/31/2017	65,054	18,566	83,620
Collaborative Research: Automated and Community-Driven Synthesis of the Tree of Life	Karen Cranston	NSF	6/1/2012 - 5/31/2015	723,338	176,656	899,994
TotalImpact.org	Heather Piowar	Alfred P. Sloan Foundation	5/1/2012 - 5/1/2013	108,696	16,304	125,000
Show Me the Evolution! Assessing Effectiveness of a New Teaching Resource	Allen Rodrigo & Kristin Jenkins	NSF	1/1/2009-12/31/2012	117,976	32,024	150,000
Meeting: The Shape of the Future: A Workshop to Consolidate and Advance the Field of Evolutionary Developmental Biology	Allen Rodrigo & Cassandra Extavour	NSF	8/1/2012 - 7/31/2014	87,503	12,495	99,998
Supplement: Women Evolving Biological Sciences	Allen Rodrigo	NSF	11/1/2012 - 12/31/2013	48,683	1,283	49,966
EAGER: NESCent Ambassador Program	Allen Rodrigo & Jory Wientraub	NSF	5/1/2011 - 4/30/2013	239,276	25,239	264,515
Evolutionary Analysis of the Histone Deacetylase Family: Biomedical Research	Allen Rodrigo (on behalf of NIH Senior Fellow Joseph Graves)	NIH	9/1/2011 - 8/31/2013	121,924	-	121,924
Spanish-Language Translation of "Evolution in the News"	Allen Rodrigo & Jory Wientraub	European Society for Evolutionary Biology	5/1/2011 - 9/30/2012	3,500	-	3,500
ABI Innovation: A Novel Database and Ontology for Evolutionary Analysis of Mammalian Feeding Physiology	Hilmar Lapp (Chris Wall)	NSF (Subaward from Duke's Dept. of Evolutionary Anthropology)	7/1/2011 - 6/30/2014	27,490	15,670	43,160
INTEROP: International Virtual Data Center for the Biodiversity, Ecological and Environmental Sciences	Hilmar Lapp (William Michener)	NSF (Subaward from Univ of New Mexico)	5/15/2008-6/30/2012	39,535	11,268	50,803
ABI Development: Ontology-Enabled Reasoning Across Phenotypes from Evolution and Model Organisms	Hilmar Lapp (Todd Vision)	NSF (Subaward from UNC-Chapel Hill)	7/1/2011-6/30/2015	Included under UNC Chapel Hill's prime award		748,394
A Digital Repository for Preservation and Sharing of Data Underlying Published Works in Evolutionary Biology	Todd Vision	NSF	9/1/2008-8/31/2012	1,900,625	279,551	2,180,176
ABI Development: Dryad: Scalable and Sustainable Infrastructure for the Publication of Data	Todd Vision	NSF	3/1/2012 - 2/29/2016	2,027,103	376,533	2,403,636
DataONE: Observation Network for Earth	Todd Vision (William Michener)	NSF (Subaward from Univ of New Mexico)	8/1/2009-12/31/2012	183,897	52,410	236,307
The iPlant Collaborative	Todd Vision & Karen Cranston	NSF (Subaward from Univ of Arizona)	10/1/10-5/31/12	13,850	3,948	17,798
TOTAL DUKE FUNDED				5,643,396	1,003,381	7,478,791

8. EXTERNALLY FUNDED RESEARCH: NESCent Grants and Proposals

FUNDED: NESCENT-UNIVERSITY OF NORTH CAROLINA						
TITLE	PI	FUNDING AGENCY	DATES	DIRECT	INDIRECT	TOTAL
A Digital Repository for Preservation and Sharing of Data Underlying Published Works in Evolutionary Biology	Jane Greenberg (Todd Vision)	NSF (Subaward from Duke Univ)	9/1/2008-8/31/2012	Included under Duke University's prime award		365,525
ABI Development: Dryad: Scalable and Sustainable Infrastructure for the Publication of Data	Todd Vision	NSF (Subaward from Duke Univ)	3/1/2012 - 2/29/2016	Included under Duke University's prime award		600,135
ABI Development: Ontology-Enabled Reasoning Across Phenotypes from Evolution and Model Organisms	Todd Vision (Paula Mabee)	NSF (Subaward from Univ of South Dakota)	7/1/2011-6/30/2015	1,127,219	178,572	1,305,791
TOTAL UNC FUNDED				1,127,219	178,572	2,271,451

FUNDED: NESCENT-NORTH CAROLINA STATE UNIVERSITY						
TITLE	PI	FUNDING AGENCY	DATES	DIRECT	INDIRECT	TOTAL
A Digital Repository for Preservation and Sharing of Data Underlying Published Works in Evolutionary Biology	Kristin Antelman (Todd Vision)	NSF (Subaward from Duke Univ)	9/1/2008-8/31/2012	Included under Duke University's prime award		134,686
ABI Development: Dryad: Scalable and Sustainable Infrastructure for the Publication of Data	Kristin Antelman (Todd Vision)	NSF (Subaward from Duke Univ)	3/1/2012 - 2/29/2016	Included under Duke University's prime award		18,827
CCLI Phase II: Extending and Enhancing Understanding Evolution for the Undergraduate Community	Brian Wiegmann (Roy Caldwell)	NSF (Subaward from UC-Berkeley)	9/1/2009-8/31/2012	22,810	5,930	28,740
TOTAL NCSU FUNDED				22,810	5,930	182,253

8. EXTERNALLY FUNDED RESEARCH: NESCent Grants and Proposals

PENDING: NESCENT-DUKE						
TITLE	PI	FUNDING AGENCY	DATES	DIRECT	INDIRECT	TOTAL
Dimensions: Diversification and Size in Metazoans	Craig McClain	NSF	1/1/2013 - 12/31/2015	452,195	122,089	574,284
Cooperation Between the EU and the US in Ecology (E-COOPEUS)	Allen Rodrigo (Dave Schimel)	NSF (Subaward from NEON)	6/1/2012 - 5/31/2014	249,941	113,687	600,135
TOTAL DUKE PENDING				702,136	235,776	937,912

PENDING: NESCENT-UNIVERSITY OF NORTH CAROLINA						
TITLE	PI	FUNDING AGENCY	DATES	DIRECT	INDIRECT	TOTAL
<i>none currently pending</i>						
TOTAL UNC PENDING				-	-	-

PENDING: NESCENT-NORTH CAROLINA STATE UNIVERSITY						
TITLE	PI	FUNDING AGENCY	DATES	DIRECT	INDIRECT	TOTAL
<i>none currently pending</i>						
TOTAL NCSU PENDING				-	-	-

TOTAL FUNDED	8,683,890
TOTAL PENDING	937,912
TOTAL FUNDED AND PENDING	9,621,802

The National Evolutionary Synthesis Center (NESCent) is a scientific research center that supports cutting-edge, cross-disciplinary research in evolution. The center offers a range of fellowships for visiting scientists and educators and sponsors numerous scientific meetings each year. NESCent is funded by the National Science Foundation and is jointly operated by Duke University, The University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, and North Carolina State University. For more information about research and training opportunities at NESCent, visit www.nescent.org.